

EFFECT OF STRAIN FIELDS ON FREQUENCY BAND GAPS OF PERIODIC LATTICE-BASED METAMATERIALS

Mohamed Shendy^a, Maen Alkhader^b, Bassam A. Abu-Nabah^c and T.A. Venkatesh^d

^aDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, American University of Sharjah, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates.
Email: b00068158@aus.edu

^bDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, American University of Sharjah, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates.
Email: malkhader@aus.edu

^cDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, American University of Sharjah, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates.
Email: babunabah@aus.edu

^dMaterials Science and Chemical Engineering, Stony Brook University, New York, USA.
Email: T.Venkatesh@stonybrook.edu

Abstract. Lattice-based metamaterials, known for their ability to deliver unique acoustic properties such as wave band gaps and direction-dependent phase velocities, are considered promising for noise filtering and acoustic sensor applications. Lattice-based metamaterials' unique acoustic abilities arise from their periodic porous structures, allowing them to be realized even when the lattices are made from isotropic materials. The properties of lattice metamaterials are primarily determined by their inner microstructure (i.e., topology and morphology). Consequently, by designing their inner microstructure, it is possible to tune their properties to filter or detect specific frequencies. Varying the topology of lattice metamaterials has been shown to affect their acoustic properties significantly. However, this work focuses on the effect of morphological changes, particularly stretching, on their acoustic properties. Stretching can be achieved by mechanically deforming lattice metamaterials using external forces or by constructing them from active constituents such as piezoelectric materials. The overall goal of this work is to assist in developing lattice metamaterial that can deliver deformation-tunable acoustic properties. This work computationally investigates the effect of stretching strain fields on a hexagonal lattice-based metamaterial. In particular, it examines the effects of small and large strain fields on the frequency band gaps between 100kHz and 1000kHz. Different strain levels are used to determine the sensitivity of frequency band gaps to stretching strains. The results show that the frequency band gaps are insensitive to small strains at low frequencies (~100kHz) but are sensitive to small strains at higher frequencies (~1000kHz). Conversely, large strains significantly affect the frequency band gaps, resulting in the shift, creation, or cancelation of band gaps. The findings demonstrate that actuating lattice-based metamaterial can effectively tune their frequency band gaps.

Keywords: Smart materials; Band gaps; Tunable properties; Finite element analysis; Lattice materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lattice-based metamaterials, known for their ability to deliver unique acoustic properties such as wave band gaps and direction-dependent phase velocities, are considered promising for applications in noise filtering and acoustic sensors [1, 2], wave attenuators [3], and wave propagation switchers [4]. The unique acoustic abilities of Lattice-based metamaterials arise from their periodic porous structures, which allow lattices to exhibit unique acoustic properties even when their struts or cell walls are made from isotropic materials. As a result, the acoustic properties of lattice metamaterials are primarily determined by their inner microstructure (i.e., topology and morphology). Consequently, by designing their inner microstructure, it is possible to tune their properties to filter or detect specific frequencies [5, 6]. While the acoustic behavior is also influenced by the constituent material, the dependence on topology is stronger and more easily engineered.

Due to the strong influence of topology on lattices' acoustic properties, multiple efforts have investigated the coupling between acoustic properties and different topologies such as hexagonal [7], Bravais [8], Auxetic [3, 9–11], Kagome [12, 13], core-embedded periodic patterns [14], and perturbed honeycombs [15–17]. These efforts

proved that frequency band gaps with different values and widths can be created or eliminated by changing lattices' topology. This observation motivated the development of lattices with designed topology to provide user-predetermined band gaps. Fulfilling this motivation was realized by utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) tools to establish a relationship between topological features and frequency band gaps [15, 17, 18]. The AI-based models were shown to be effective in selecting the geometric features needed to deliver a specific band gap. The potential for designing lattice materials with specific band gaps motivated the development of lattices with tunable properties. These lattices can potentially change their acoustic properties due to their interaction with their environments, such as interacting with electric, voltage, force, or thermal fields. The working principle of these materials is based on external excitation inducing a morphological change in the lattice structure, which subsequently alters their acoustic properties. Accordingly, the sensitivity of band gaps in lattice materials to morphological changes caused by deformations triggered by external stimuli such as uniform loading, buckling instabilities, or thermal and electrical fields has been explored. [4–6, 19–22]. Results demonstrated that frequency band gaps could be activated or deactivated by deformations that significantly morph lattice materials. These findings supported the hypothesis that the band gaps of lattice materials can be tailored by adjusting their inner structure [15]. However, advancing this approach requires a deeper understanding of the limitations of tunability through morphing. Although a broader range of morphing is linked to more tunable responses, excessive morphing can significantly alter the lattice's shape, potentially causing overstress and damage. Therefore, it is essential to define the tunable range of lattices when using morphing. This involves assessing the impact of small to relatively large shape changes on the acoustic properties of the lattices. Understanding these limitations will aid in designing the mechanisms that drive morphing. For instance, knowing the deformable limits of a lattice can assist in selecting its constituent material (e.g., active materials), trigger mechanisms, and the desired tunable frequency band gap range.

This work focuses on investigating the effect of morphological changes on the acoustic properties of lattices. These changes are modeled by uniform stretching fields, which represent uniform axial strains. Such strains can be generated or triggered by external forces [5] or by external electric fields when the lattices are composed of active materials, such as piezoelectric constituents. The effect of these stretching strain fields on the band gaps of hexagonal and triangular lattice-based metamaterials is analyzed using computational techniques. Specifically, this study examines the impact of both small and large strain fields on the frequency band gaps of the lattices in the 100 kHz to 1000 kHz range. Various strain levels are applied to assess the sensitivity of the frequency band gaps to stretching strains (i.e., morphing). The overall aim of this work is to support the development of lattice metamaterials with deformation-tunable acoustic properties.

2 METHODOLOGY

The effect of stretching-induced morphing is investigated in a hexagonal honeycomb lattice. This lattice is chosen due to its widespread use as cores in composite sandwich structures, making it industrially relevant. Additionally, it represents the class of lattices in which the underlying deformation mechanism of their cell walls is bending. The hexagonal lattice is comprised of identical cell walls in terms of material property and thickness. Thus, this cell follows the single-sided cell wall classification. The lattice is assumed to be made of aluminum with Young's modulus of 70 GPa, Poisson's ratio of 0.33, and a density of 2700 kg/m³. The lattice is 10 mm in size. Size is defined as the distance from one corner of the hexagon to the opposing corner. Accordingly, the circle passing through the six corners of the hexagon is 10 mm in diameter. Multiple relative densities are considered, namely 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%, to explore the effect of relative densities. Larger relative densities are not considered as highly porous materials exhibit richer frequency band gap behavior in terms of frequency level and bandwidth. In addition, larger relative densities will correlate to higher mass and less flexible structures. The methodology investigated the response in an infinite material, which is represented using the unit cell approach. The unit cell used to represent the honeycomb lattice is shown in Figure 1. Two levels of stretching are used, namely 3% and 12%. The former represents a relatively small morphing strain, while the latter represents a considerable morphing strain. Although morphing in applications can comprise deformations in multiple directions, one one-directional stretching is considered to facilitate focusing on the interaction of strain and frequency band gaps. Similar studies can subsequently be used to investigate other morphing strain directions or the effect of combined strains.

The determination of the frequency band gaps for both the regular and stretched hexagonal lattices is conducted using finite element analysis in conjunction with Bloch wave theory. While the complete

methodology is detailed in the literature [17], it is briefly summarized here to provide readers with sufficient background without unnecessary repetition. The approach starts by defining the physical lattice directions ($\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2$) and their reciprocal directions ($\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2$). The physical lattice directions are shown in Figure 2 for the unstretched lattice. For the stretched lattice, they will rotate slightly upward.

Figure 1: Schematic of the hexagonal honeycomb lattice and its unit cell, showing the configuration before and after stretching

The reciprocal vectors are computed from the physical vectors using the definition $\mathbf{b}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_j = \delta_{ij}$, where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta. The two reciprocal lattice vectors are used to define the 1st Brillouin zone. This zone for the unstretched lattice is shown in Figure 2. The 1st Brillouin zone for the stretched lattice would change slightly since both its physical and reciprocal lattice vectors would be altered.

Figure 2: The lattice vectors and 1st Brillouin zone for the unstretched hexagonal lattice.

Applying the Bloch wave theory on the unit cell results in the periodic boundary conditions that describe the propagation of a harmonic wave with specific attenuation and dispersion properties in the periodic lattice. The periodic boundary conditions for both the unstretched and stretched lattices are given by

$$\text{and} \tag{1}$$

such that $\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2$ represent the degrees of freedom at the nodes 0, 1, and 2 shown in Figure 2, respectively. and k_2 represent the dispersive properties along the reciprocal directions, which are defined using

$$\tag{2}$$

The range of admissible values of k_1 and k_2 is defined by the 1st Brillouin zone [17]. The periodic boundary conditions defined by Equation (1) are applied to the unit cell shown in Figure 2 using the finite element software ABAQUS. The walls of the unit cell were modeled using Timoshenko beam elements. Each wall was discretized using at least 50 elements. This number was determined after conducting a mesh sensitivity analysis, which identified 50 as the conservative number to ensure that the results are independent of the mesh size. The periodic boundary conditions were applied using the Equation command in ABAQUS. The default

eigenfrequency solver in ABAQUS, the Lanczos solver, was used to calculate the eigenfrequencies of the models, which consisted of a unit cell and periodic boundary conditions. Only eigenfrequencies below 1000 kHz were determined. The solution process requires assuming the k_1 and k_2 values before solving the systems to find their eigenvalues. The values of k_1 and k_2 are defined by tracing the polygon marked by the points OABCO in Figure 2. Each line of the polygon was divided into 20 segments. Each point on the segments belonging to the polygon OABCO defines a set of k_1 and k_2 . So, for each point on the polygon OABCO, the system was solved, and the eigenfrequencies were determined. The eigenfrequencies were plotted against the position on the polygon OABCO. This plot defines the band gap structure, with the gaps representing the frequency band gaps.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The described approach was used to determine the frequency band gaps in the unstretched, 3% stretched, and 12% stretched lattices at the relative densities of 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%. Results are shown in Figure 3. In this figure, each frequency band gap detected is presented as a bar whose lower level and upper level correspond to the boundaries of the frequency band gap. The figure is color-coded to represent the frequency band gap level in kHz. Results show that the unstretched lattice had two to three frequency band gaps at almost every relative density tested, except at the highest relative density. At increased relative density, the porosity decreases, and so do the band gaps. However, stretching the lattice by 3%, which is reasonably low, affected the frequency band gaps at the lowest densities most. The stretching caused two gaps to vanish at 5% relative density. Additionally, it caused one band to disappear at each of the relative densities: 10%, 15%, 25%, and 30%.

Figure 3: The frequency band gaps of the unstretched, 3% stretched, and 12% stretched lattices.

Higher stretch, i.e., 12% strain, resulted in a more pronounced effect. It eliminated all the band gaps at the relative densities of 5%, 15%, 25%, and 30%. It also reduced the width of the frequency band gaps. Conversely, it generated two new band gaps at 10% relative density. Moreover, the lowest band, at 20% relative density, was shifted downward. Accordingly, the results demonstrate a significant change in the frequency band gap characteristics due to the application of stretching or morphing strain.

Results indicate that frequency band gaps nonlinearly depend on relative density. Both the width and level of the band gaps varied with relative density, but the lowest number of band gaps was observed at the highest relative density used. From an application perspective, e.g., sensing or filtering, small morphing-induced strains can make the lattice sensitivity to a few frequencies. Those are the frequency band gaps that were eliminated by

the small strain, such as the ~ 580 kHz at 5% relative density. Frequencies around this range would be blocked by the original lattice, but they will be allowed to pass by the 3% deformed lattice. Accordingly, a 3% strain can be considered an on/off switch to pass frequencies around ~ 580 kHz. The on-off switching is more effective at the 12% strain. This strain can close all the gates at 5%, 15%, 25%, and 30%. But even at 10% and 20%, the 12% strain decreased the width of the frequency band gaps and decreased their functionality; they can just pass a very narrow range of frequencies. So, the 12% strain can be practically used to block the propagation of all frequencies below 1000 kHz. Accordingly, strains between 3% and 12% are significant enough to alter the acoustic properties of the hexagonal lattice and change its frequency band gaps. The strains achieve this effect by changing the inner structure of the lattice. This change in inner structure stems from the linear transformation associated with stretching the lattice, which can be achieved in practical applications by applying an external force. Of course, other approaches can be used to deform and stretch the lattice, such as utilizing active or shape memory materials and subsequently triggering the lattice deformation using a thermal, electrical, or magnetic external field. The mechanism of deforming the lattice is not within the scope of this work. Here, we are focused on finding the level of deformation (i.e., morphing) that can effectively lead to significant changes in the acoustic properties of the lattice material. So, the results suggest that strains beyond 12% are not needed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- This work's main objective was to explore the effect of applying morphing strain fields on the frequency band gaps of a common lattice (i.e., Hexagonal honeycomb lattice) over a range of porosity or relative density levels. Small (3%) and large (12%) strain fields were used to represent actuating-induced strains.
- Frequency band gaps showed nonlinear dependence on porosity or relative density level. However, smaller porosities exhibited narrower and lesser frequency band gaps.
- Both applied strains affected the frequency band gaps of the lattice. The small strain, 3%, effectively eliminated multiple frequency band gaps. On the other hand, The large strain, 12%, eliminated all band gaps at 5%, 15%, 25%, and 30% relative densities. It also narrowed all remaining frequency band gaps at the 10% and 20 % relative densities. Accordingly, the large strain altered the behavior of the lattice to block approximately most frequencies below 1000 kHz.
- Results confirm that strains between 3% and 12% can be used effectively to switch the frequency band gaps of the hexagonal lattice on and off. Accordingly, from an application perspective, to utilize this lattice as a frequency switch or sensor, it should be morphed by strains within the 12% range. This morphing strain can be generated by an external force or by the use of active constitutes.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was funded by the American University of Sharjah under Grant FRG23-C-E09. This paper represents the opinions of the author(s) and does not mean to represent the position or opinions of the American University of Sharjah.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Chen, F. Qian, L. Zuo, F. Scarpa, and L. Wang, "Broadband and multiband vibration mitigation in lattice metamaterials with sinusoidally-shaped ligaments," *Extreme Mech Lett*, vol. 17, pp. 24–32, 2017.
- [2] M. Shendy, M. Alkhader, B. A. Abu-Nabah, M. A. Jaradat, and T. A. Venkatesh, "Machine learning assisted approach to design lattice materials with prescribed band gap characteristics," *European Journal of Mechanics - A/Solids*, vol. 102, p. 105125, 2023.
- [3] M. Kheybari, C. Daraio, and O. R. Bilal, "Tunable auxetic metamaterials for simultaneous attenuation of airborne sound and elastic vibrations in all directions," *Appl Phys Lett*, vol. 121, no. 8, 2022.
- [4] C. Gao, V. Slesarenko, M. C. Boyce, S. Rudykh, and Y. Li, "Instability-induced pattern transformation in soft metamaterial with hexagonal networks for tunable wave propagation," *Sci Rep*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 11834, 2018.
- [5] K. Bertoldi and M. C. Boyce, "Wave propagation and instabilities in monolithic and periodically structured elastomeric materials undergoing large deformations," *Phys Rev B*, vol. 78, no. 18, p. 184107, 2008.
- [6] K. Bertoldi, V. Vitelli, J. Christensen, and M. van Hecke, "Flexible mechanical metamaterials," *Nat Rev Mater*, vol. 2, no. 11, p. 17066, 2017.

- [7] S. Gonella and M. Ruzzene, "Analysis of in-plane wave propagation in hexagonal and re-entrant lattices," *J Sound Vib*, vol. 312, no. 1, pp. 125–139, 2008.
- [8] S. Iyer, M. Alkhader, and T. A. ; A. Venkatesh, "Band Gaps in Bravais Lattices Inspired Periodic Cellular Materials and the Effect of Relative Density and Strain Fields," in *ASME 2014 International Mechanical Engineering Congress & Exposition*, Montreal, Canada: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2014, p. V013T16A022-V013T16A022.
- [9] M. Ruzzene and F. Scarpa, "Directional and band-gap behavior of periodic auxetic lattices," *physica status solidi (b)*, vol. 242, no. 3, pp. 665–680, 2005.
- [10] S. Mukherjee, F. Scarpa, and S. Gopalakrishnan, "Phononic band gap design in honeycomb lattice with combinations of auxetic and conventional core," *Smart Mater Struct*, vol. 25, no. 5, p. 54011, 2016.
- [11] P. Eghbali, D. Younesian, and S. Farhangdoust, "Enhancement of the low-frequency acoustic energy harvesting with auxetic resonators," *Appl Energy*, vol. 270, p. 115217, 2020.
- [12] B. Niu and B. Wang, "Directional mechanical properties and wave propagation directionality of Kagome honeycomb structures," *European Journal of Mechanics - A/Solids*, vol. 57, pp. 45–58, 2016.
- [13] Y. Liu, X. Sun, W. Jiang, and Y. Gu, "Tuning of bandgap structures in three-dimensional Kagome-sphere lattice," *J Vib Acoust*, vol. 136, no. 2, 2014.
- [14] J. Hou, Z. Zhang, and D. Li, "Numerical and experimental study on bandgap property of two-dimensional lattice with nested core," *Applied Physics A*, vol. 128, no. 2, p. 164, 2022.
- [15] M. Shendy, M. A. Jaradat, M. Alkhader, B. A. Abu-Nabah, and T. A. Venkatesh, "Hybrid intelligent framework for designing band gap-rich 2D metamaterials," *Int J Solids Struct*, vol. 304, p. 113053, 2024.
- [16] C. W. Lim, "Phononic metastructures with ultrawide low frequency three-dimensional bandgaps as broadband low frequency filter," *Sci Rep*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–11, 2021.
- [17] A. R. Diaz, A. G. Haddow, and L. Ma, "Design of band-gap grid structures," *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 418–431, 2005.
- [18] M. Alkhader, S. Iyer, W. Shi, and T. A. Venkatesh, "Low frequency acoustic characteristics of periodic honeycomb cellular cores: The effect of relative density and strain fields," *Compos Struct*, vol. 133, pp. 77–84, 2015.
- [19] S. Singamaneni et al., "Bifurcated Mechanical Behavior of Deformed Periodic Porous Solids," *Adv Funct Mater*, vol. 19, no. 9, pp. 1426–1436, 2009.
- [20] K. Bertoldi and M. C. Boyce, "Mechanically triggered transformations of phononic band gaps in periodic elastomeric structures," *Phys Rev B*, vol. 77, no. 5, p. 52105, 2008.
- [21] S. Yang, X. Zhou, and Y.-F. Wang, "Tunable band gap and wave guiding in periodic grid structures with thermal sensitive materials," *Compos Struct*, vol. 290, p. 115536, 2022.